

INFORMATION SOURCES CITED IN THE ASSESSMENT AND SELECTION OF THE DEGREE OF RISK OF TOURISM DESTINATIONS

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ABSTRACT

The article explains the nature of risks and highlights the danger they pose and the impact of threats on tourists' behavior, travel, and destination choices. It examines the assessment of risks, determining the degree of riskiness of a destination, and the sources tourists rely on when making their choices, and highlights the importance of taking the reliability of those sources as a basis.

Keywords: tourism, risk, degree of risk of destination, source of Information, choice of destination.

1.Introduction. It is known that in recent years, the geopolitical, economic and social situation in many regions of the world has been deteriorating for various reasons. The conditions created by globalization require various authorities to take certain measures in their own interests, which creates various dangers and threats to other countries, economic development, globally significant socio-cultural processes and activities. In addition, terrorist attacks and threats from radical groups, the emergence of ethnic, religious, and national conflicts and wars, the spread of infectious diseases and epidemics, increased crime, economic turmoil, increased uncertainty, and other factors increase risks in most sectors of the economy. This circumstance also increases the likelihood of certain risks in tourism. The multifaceted nature of tourism activities, their interrelations and connections with most sectors of the economic system, significantly increase the likelihood of risk. The negative effects of risks create serious problems for most tourism destinations, tourism enterprises, tourism management structures and tourism businesses and negatively affect the development of the tourism industry. The high sensitivity of tourism industry sectors to internal and external factors makes them more vulnerable to threats and events caused by risks.

In any case, the high probability of risk threats creates a serious obstacle to the development of tourism in countries and the world, reduces tourist flows, limits its role in solving important socio-economic problems, and hinders the implementation of its important functions. In conflict regions where different interests collide, the duration, stability of uncertainty conditions, threats of natural and anthropogenic origin, etc. increase the likelihood of tourist risks, manifesting themselves more acutely. At the same time, tourists avoid visiting risky regions and analyze various sources of information to learn the level of risk in that region, understand the possible risks, and decide to travel based on their conclusions.

2.Relevance of the topic. The rapid development of tourism, along with creating positive effects, also increases the probability of certain dangers and risks. This creates an obstacle to the sustainable development of tourism and reduces the desire of tourists to travel to some extent. The level of riskiness of tourist destinations and centers affects tourists' decisions to travel. Tourists turn to various information sources to obtain reliable information about the riskiness of the trip and

the perception of risks. The article characterizes tourism risks and the information sources that tourists refer to to learn the riskiness of trips. The article provides for a study of the issues raised, so its relevance is beyond doubt.

3.The purpose of the study. It is planned to develop proposals for a better understanding by tourists of the likely risks in destinations, the choice of reliable channels for obtaining information that affects the perception of risks in the process of choosing a destination.

4.Discussion. In general, risk is essentially understood as “a probable or possible danger, loss, injury or other negative impact”, “an event that an object or subject is exposed to danger or suffers damage”. Here, the term “risk” is interpreted mainly in the context of creating negative consequences. In the second case, taking a risk, a risky event can also lead to a positive outcome. The third possibility is that the risk is related to the uncertainty of the outcome [4, p. 15-16]. At the same time, approaches to the nature of risks in various standards and studies are characterized by the identification of certain features. For example, according to ISO Guide 73 ISO 31000, risk is defined as “the positive or negative impact of uncertainty on an objective, deviation from an expected outcome, change in the situation or adverse outcome resulting from the frequent occurrence of an event.” According to the Institute for Risk Management (IRM), “risk is the combination of the probability of an event occurring and its positive or negative consequences.” The Institute of Internal Auditors (IIA) defines risk as “the uncertainty associated with the occurrence of an event that could affect the achievement of objectives, measured in terms of its consequences and probability”.

Risk in tourism is the probability of a certain dangerous, harmful event occurring and its possible negative consequences. Risks in tourism mainly affect the safety, health, financial, reputational and operational areas. UNWTO characterizes risks in tourism as “the set of internal and external factors that affect the safety and sustainability of tourists, personnel and tourism facilities” [6].

In tourism, several types of risk are usually distinguished. Researchers distinguish the presence of the following types of risk:

Health risks. Health risks usually pose a threat to the physical health of tourists. Health risks include food shortages and safety, sanitation, infectious diseases, ep-

idemics, pandemics, seasonal and climate-related diseases. Infectious disease in tourism is considered a global risk and threat [7, p 37].

Security risks. It is known that in the hierarchy of needs of people, as well as tourists, the demand for security is in second place. Therefore, ensuring security in tourism is one of the urgent issues, and the management and Prevention of this type of risk is included in the main tasks. This risk group includes terrorist acts, crime (theft, robbery), unstable political situation, riots of various origins, war, armed conflicts [1].

The group of natural risks includes forest fires, hurricanes, storms, landslides, earthquakes, floods, tsunamis, etc. This group of risks is known for creating more serious negative consequences and severely affects the development of tourism and tourism infrastructure [5].

One of the risks that cause serious damage in tourism activities is operational risks. The occurrence of operational risks is associated with the adoption of erroneous decisions, technical malfunctions of equipment, delays in transport services, low quality of Service, lack of personnel and incompetence of personnel.

Since financial stability and provision in tourism is an important factor in the sustainable development of the industry, financial risks have dire consequences. Economic fluctuations and crises, changes in the exchange rate, increased inflation, high bank rates, weakness of insurance activities are the main causes of this type of risk.

The successful operation of tourism enterprises, their longevity, competitiveness, the quality of the services they offer, directly affect the formation of their reputation, but at the same time pose certain risks. Reputation risks include complaints about the quality of services, the spread of negative opinion about the enterprise as a result of the spread of dissatisfaction of tourists on social media, the creation of environmental losses by tourism enterprises, etc. Reputation risks reduce the loyalty of tourists to enterprises and destinations, and this leads to a decrease in income and bankruptcy.

Due to the fact that tourism activity is more associated with natural resources and environmental factors, there is a high probability of the impact of environmental risks on its Sustainable Development. The massive influx of tourists to certain territories and destinations increases the anthropogenic impact on the environment, damages flora and fauna, biodiversity. As a result, the likelihood of exposure to the risks of environmental pollution, biodiversity decline, climate change, ecosystem disruption in tourism activities increases [2].

The development of tourism and the dynamic growth of tourist trips are associated with awareness of the perceived tourist risks in tourist destinations and the choice of this factor. Information should be cited in order to understand the risks in advance, and this information comes from certain sources. The reliability of sources is one of the important conditions to avoid mistakes when making decisions.

It should be noted that the issues of perception and risk assessment in tourism activities are highly relevant. At the same time, the classification of the types of

emerging or probable risks according to various criteria, the study of the causes of their occurrence, remain incomplete and specified. The growing influence of many factors, especially risks, on tourism activities requires a more systematic and consistent study of risk-related issues, as well as focusing on their perception and identifying reliable sources of information to clarify the level of riskiness of destinations.

Tourists use numerous means and information resources to perceive and assess risks, and choosing destinations [3]. The funds and resources referred to in this case can generally be divided into two groups:

1. Making decisions on the basis of personal judgments, experiences and internal convictions;
2. Making decisions based on information obtained from external sources.

Tourists, when perceiving and assessing the riskiness of destinations in the first case, mainly refer to:

- personal experience with the destinations they had been to before and were happy with;
- their personal assessment of the risk level of the environment in the destination during the previous visit;
- the experience they have about the destination that creates confidence and motivation for them;
- to the reviews of friends and acquaintances whom they consider reliable;
- to information from sources where individual tourists share their real experiences and reviews (personal accounts on social networks, personal blogs and video blogs).

It is advisable to specifically consider the role of personal experience and personal qualities of tourists in the perception of risk and the choice of destination. The most reliable source of reference in the perception and assessment of any risk, choosing a destination, of course, can be the personal experience of a tourist. For this reason, tourists, relying on personal experience and based on the perceptions and impressions of previous trips, more confidently decide to use the services of destinations that offer and deliver better and more affordable tourist products and services in a safe environment.

Usually, tourists, based on previous experience, using the opportunity to analyze the probability of risk at the destination and its outcome, can come to the conclusion about the presence or absence of any threats during the trip, which affects the decision on the choice. At the same time, in a previously visited destination, there are more opportunities to plan and prepare for a risky situation in advance, without incurring any damage or any damage.

In addition to making decisions based on personal judgments, experience and inner conviction when perceiving and assessing risks and choosing a destination, tourists can also rely on their intuition, the opinion of people who have made decisions in similar situations, the experience, advice and recommendations of the local population of the region in which the destination is located, experienced tour organizers, guides and organizations, providing consulting services in the field of tourism.

The second area of resources and tools that tourists refer to for risk perception and decision-making is the following:

Advertising and information resources and tools:

- official warnings and recommendations of various state security structures, ministries, committees, state tourism management bodies, tourism enterprises and organizations about risks and dangers;

- news about possible threats, weather forecast for the period covering the tour period;

- information about natural disasters, local and regional political situation;

Facebook Instagram, Facebook, Twitter (X), LinkedIn, TripAdvisor, etc.);

- information from traditional global (National Geographic Travel, Tourism Review, Travel Daily News, TTG Media, Skift, TurboNews, Travel Weekly) and local media, which also provide tourism news;

- information obtained by word of mouth (acquaintances, friends, relatives, family members);

- national, regional and local official TV, radio channels, print media, government websites, state media, mass media of tourism authorities, etc.;

- official channels, websites of tourist enterprises and organizations, destinations, means of distributing special tourist information (booklets, brochures, catalogs, newsletters, etc.).

Technological tools and applications.

It is important to note the importance and role of using applications that warn about risks and threats, dangerous events, in risk perception and destination selection. TripWhistle, Safeture (applications for warning about risks), Google Public Alerts (an application that warns on a map about earthquakes, storms and floods), Google Maps, Maps.me (mapping and navigation applications for choosing safe routes), etc. belong to such applications.

In addition, some countries use alert programs and applications in risky situations. For example, in Azerbaijan and Russia, one can mention the 112 mobile application for contacting the emergency service of the Ministry of Emergency Situations, the SMS alerts application, which sends information in case of earthquakes, fires, floods, etc.; in the USA, FEMA programs with emergency preparedness and alerts, MyShake, which provides early warning of earthquakes and Red Cross Emergency, which alerts about emergencies, AccuWeather and Windy applications, which provide information about extreme weather events, etc. In Germany, NINA, KATWARN, BIWAPP applications are used in risky situations; in France, FR-Alert (system), Météo-France App, and in many European countries, the European Emergency Number Association (112 App) applications.

Considering the above, we propose to group all the resources and tools used and referenced in the process

of risk perception and assessment, destination selection, as follows:

- social networks and platforms, online resources;

- official (state) sources of information;

- information tools of the state tourism management bodies;

- websites and advertising and information tools of tourist enterprises and organizations;

- traditional electronic and print media;

- special tourist information channels, portals and websites;

- various technological tools (programs and applications);

- personal experience, worldview, intuition;

- word-of-mouth and personal information.

5. Conclusion. Tourists access and reference to various information resources in order to make a decision on choosing a destination and understanding the risks depends on the availability of these resources, the level of skills of tourists and the development of methods of using modern information databases. The appeal and reference of tourists to information sources is also related to social, individual, psychological, demographic, economic and other factors. Based on observations, it can be said that among the older generation of tourists, there is an increasing tendency to receive information from the Internet and other electronic and digital sources and refer to this information in the process of perceiving and assessing risks and choosing destinations.

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